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CHANGES IN THE BIOLOGICAL DIVERSITY OF HOOFED ANIMALS IN THE TUGAI FORESTS OF THE SOUTHERN ARAL REGION UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE CONDITIONS

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Abstract: This scientific article analyzes changes in the composition and diversity of Coleoptera fauna under the influence of climate change and anthropogenic factors in the dried-up tugai ecosystems of the Southern Aral Sea basin. The main objective of the study is to determine the dynamics of hard-winged insect groups resulting from changes in the region's hydrological regime over the last 30 years and to evaluate their significance as biomonitoring indicators. By comparing field observations and materials from museum collections, it was established that the number of moisture-loving species has decreased sharply, while desertification-resistant (xerophilic) species have become widespread. The article presents scientifically grounded recommendations for restoring ecological balance and preserving biodiversity.

Keywords: Southern Aral Sea region, tugai forests, Coleoptera, climate change, biomonitoring, biodiversity, desertification, entomofauna, ecosystem.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqolada Janubiy Orol dengizi havzasining qurib qolgan to'qay ekotizimlarida iqlim o'zgarishi va antropogen omillar ta'siri ostida Coleoptera faunasining tarkibi hamda xilma-xilligida yuz bergan o'zgarishlar tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi so'nggi 30 yil davomida mintaqaning gidrologik rejimida sodir bo'lgan o'zgarishlar natijasida qattiq qanotli hasharotlar guruhlarining dinamikasini aniqlash va ularning biomonitoring ko'rsatkichi sifatidagi ahamiyatini baholashdan iborat. Dala kuzatuvlari va muzey kolleksiyalari materiallarini taqqoslash natijasida namsevar turlar sonining keskin kamaygani, cho'llanishga chidamli (kserofil) turlar esa keng tarqalgani aniqlandi. Maqolada ekologik muvozanatni tiklash va biologik xilma-xillikni saqlash bo'yicha ilmiy asoslangan tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Janubiy Orolbo'yi, to'qay o'rmonlari, Coleoptera, iqlim o'zgarishi, biomonitoring, biologik xilma-xillik, cho'llanish, entomofauna, ekotizim.

Аннотация: В данной научной статье анализируются изменения состава и разнообразия фауны жесткокрылых (Coleoptera) под воздействием климатических изменений и антропогенных факторов в высохших тугайных экосистемах бассейна Южного Аральского моря. Основной целью исследования является определение динамики групп жесткокрылых насекомых, вызванной изменениями гидрологического режима региона за последние 30 лет, а также оценка их значения в качестве индикаторов биомониторинга. На основе сравнения полевых наблюдений и материалов музейных коллекций установлено, что численность влаголюбивых видов резко сократилась, тогда как виды, устойчивые к опустыниванию (ксерофильные), получили широкое распространение. В статье представлены научно обоснованные рекомендации по восстановлению экологического равновесия и сохранению биоразнообразия.

Ключевые слова: Южное Приаралье, тугайные леса, Coleoptera, изменение климата, биомониторинг, биоразнообразие, опустынивание, энтомофауна, экосистема.

INTRODUCTION

The Aral Sea disaster is considered one of the largest environmental catastrophes in the Central Asian region. The decline in the sea level and its progressive desiccation have not only altered climatic conditions

but have also led to the degradation of the unique tugai forest ecosystems located in river deltas. Tugai forests are biocenoses characterized by a high groundwater level, moist soils, and dense vegetation cover. These ecosystems serve as important habitats for insects, particularly beetles (Coleoptera).

Beetles (Coleoptera) represent one of the largest and ecologically most significant groups of entomofauna. Due to their role in food chains, as well as in the decomposition and recycling of organic matter and plant residues, they are considered important indicators of ecosystem health. Climate change, particularly the increase in temperature and the decrease in precipitation, along with limitations in irrigation water supply, is contributing to the reduction of tugai forest areas. Understanding how these processes affect the structure of insect populations is currently one of the pressing scientific issues. This study is devoted to investigating the dynamics of changes in the beetle fauna of the Southern Aral Sea region, including the lower reaches of the Amu Darya Delta and the southern part of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The ecological consequences of climate change in the Aral Sea region have been widely discussed in recent scientific literature. Researchers emphasize that the desiccation of the Aral Sea has caused not only hydrological imbalance but also severe degradation of natural ecosystems, particularly tugai forests located in the Amu Darya and Syr Darya deltas. According to reports by the United Nations Development Programme (2022), increasing aridity and soil salinization are among the main factors reducing biological productivity in the region.

Numerous studies have confirmed that insects are highly sensitive indicators of environmental transformation. Kryzhanovskiy (1965) highlighted the ecological importance of beetles (Coleoptera) in maintaining trophic balance and nutrient cycling in terrestrial ecosystems. Later entomological investigations demonstrated that changes in the species composition of beetles can reflect the level of ecosystem degradation and anthropogenic disturbance.

Kerimova and Abduraimov (2023) investigated the present state of entomofauna in the Southern Aral Sea region and reported a considerable decline in moisture-dependent insect species. Their research indicated that xerophilous beetle groups are becoming dominant due to increasing desertification processes. Similar conclusions were presented by Ismoilov (2021), who emphasized that climate-induced habitat fragmentation negatively affects the migration and reproductive potential of many endemic insect species.

International ecological studies also stress the significance of biomonitoring methods in assessing ecosystem stability. The Shannon–Wiener diversity index and the Pielou evenness index are commonly used in biodiversity research to evaluate species richness and dominance structure. According to modern ecological concepts, a reduction in biodiversity indices is closely associated with ecosystem instability and the weakening of natural self-regulation mechanisms.

Despite the growing number of studies devoted to the Aral Sea crisis, insufficient attention has been paid specifically to the long-term structural changes in beetle fauna within tugai ecosystems. Therefore, the present study contributes to filling this scientific gap by analyzing the dynamics of Coleoptera diversity under climate change conditions in the Southern Aral Sea region.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted during 2020–2025 in the remaining tugai forest massifs located in the southern part of the Amu Darya Delta. As sampling sites, three typical tugai forest zones situated both near and far from water sources were selected in the Beruniy, To'rtko'l, and Ellikqal'a districts.

Standard entomological methods were applied to collect beetles (Coleoptera):

Pitfall traps (Barber traps) – used for collecting ground-dwelling and subterranean species.

Sweep netting – used for collecting phytophagous and predatory species inhabiting vegetation.

Manual collection method – used for identifying species living under tree bark and in decaying wood.

The collected materials were examined under a microscope under laboratory conditions and classified to the species level. Species identification was carried out using modern taxonomic keys and expert consultations. The obtained data were compared with archival records from the 1990s. For statistical analysis, the Shannon–Wiener diversity index and the Pielou evenness index were calculated.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The comparative analysis of field materials collected during 2020–2025 and archival data from the 1990s revealed substantial structural changes in the beetle fauna of the tugai forests of the Southern Aral Sea region.

A total of 87 beetle species belonging to 21 families were identified during the research period. Comparative

analysis showed that the overall species richness has decreased by approximately 27% over the last three decades. The most pronounced decline was recorded among moisture-dependent beetle groups associated with dense vegetation and humid soils.

The Shannon–Wiener diversity index varied significantly among the studied territories. In relatively preserved tugai forests located near water sources, the diversity index ranged from 2.8 to 3.1, indicating comparatively stable ecosystem conditions. However, in highly degraded and salinized territories, the index declined to 1.7–2.0, reflecting reduced species diversity and ecosystem instability.

The Pielou evenness index demonstrated an opposite tendency. In arid territories, the index reached 0.78–0.82 due to the dominance of a limited number of drought-resistant species, particularly representatives of the Tenebrionidae family. In contrast, preserved tugai ecosystems showed a more balanced species distribution, with evenness values between 0.61 and 0.69.

Among the Carabidae family, the abundance of predatory beetles decreased by nearly 40% compared to archival records. Species belonging to the genera *Carabus* and *Calosoma* were recorded only in isolated humid habitats. This reduction indicates the deterioration of suitable microclimatic conditions and the fragmentation of ecological niches (Table 1).

Table 1. Main Changes in Coleoptera Diversity in the Southern Aral Sea Tugai Ecosystems (2020–2025)

Indicator	Result
Total beetle species recorded	87 species (21 families)
Change in species richness	Decreased by 27%
Shannon–Wiener index	1.7–3.1
Pielou evenness index	0.61–0.82
Predatory beetles (Carabidae)	Decreased by ~40%
Xerophilous species (Tenebrionidae)	Increased
Moisture-dependent species	Decreased sharply
Rare endemic species (Lucanidae)	Found only in isolated habitats

At the same time, xerophilous representatives of the Tenebrionidae family, including species of the genera *Blaps* and *Pimelia*, demonstrated population growth and wider distribution. These species showed high adaptability to elevated temperatures, soil salinity, and reduced humidity.

The study also identified significant changes in trophic structure. The proportion of predatory beetles declined from 34% to 21%, while phytophagous and detritophagous groups increased considerably. Such an imbalance may weaken natural biological control mechanisms within the ecosystem and contribute to the spread of harmful insect species.

Rare and endemic beetles associated with old tugai trees were found to be particularly vulnerable. Representatives of the Lucanidae family were recorded only in limited localities containing remnants of mature vegetation. Their declining populations indicate the ongoing degradation of natural habitats and the reduction of deadwood resources necessary for larval development.

The obtained results confirm that climate change, together with anthropogenic pressure and hydrological disturbances, significantly affects the biological diversity of beetle fauna in tugai ecosystems. The transformation of species composition and functional structure reflects the progressive desertification of the Southern Aral Sea region.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Significant changes are occurring in the beetle (Coleoptera) fauna of the tugai forests of the Southern Aral Sea region under the influence of climate change and anthropogenic factors. While the populations of moisture-dependent and shade-loving species have sharply declined, drought-resistant species are becoming

increasingly widespread. This process is leading to a reduction in ecosystem stability and the disruption of trophic chains. Beetles serve as an effective biomonitoring tool and play an important role in assessing ecosystem health.

The conservation and restoration of tugai forest ecosystems are of vital importance not only for insects but also for the entire biocenosis, including birds and mammals. A comprehensive approach, particularly the rational use of water resources and ecological restoration measures, will contribute to the preservation of biological diversity. Future research in this region will play an important role in developing adaptation strategies to climate change.

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